

Soil and crop management

Response of deepwater rice to nitrogen fertilizer in fluxial ecology in Nigeria

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A 2-year trial (1978-79) at the RRS at Birnin-Kebbi studied the effect of time of nitrogen application on the yield of deepwater rice in the naturally inundated ecology in northern Nigeria where rice is traditionally grown on a vast hectareage.

Nitrogen at 67 kg/ha was applied as a single dose and in various split doses at sowing (worked into soil) 15 days and 30 days after sowing (basal dressing on wet soil) (see table). At the time of sowing 37 kg P₂O₅/ha was incorporated into the soil as, a blanket application. The source of nitrogen and P₂O₅ were calcium ammonium nitrate and single superphosphate. The plots had 30-cm-high bunds.

A long-duration (180 days), tall, photoperiod-sensitive rice variety FARO-14, well adapted to deep flood

Effect of time of nitrogen application on grain yield of deepwater rice variety FARO-14. Birnin - Kebbi, Nigeria, 1978-79.

Treatment no.	Time and split dose of 67 kg N/h ^a			Grain yield ^b (t/ha)		
	AS	15 DS	30 DS	1978	1979	Mean
1	67	0	0	4.33	5.34 abcd	4.84 ab
2	0	67	0	3.97	4.96 cd	4.47 bc
3	0	0	67	4.31	5.31 abcd	4.82 ab
4	22.3	22.3	22.4	3.88	4.94 cd	4.41 bc
5	33.5	33.5	0	4.06	5.39 abcd	4.73 ab
6	33.5	0	33.5	4.13	5.59 abed	4.86 ab
7	16.7	33.5	16.8	3.93	5.07 bcd	4.51 bc
8	33.5	16.7	16.8	4.82	5.76 abc	5.29 a
9	15.7	16.8	33.5	4.24	5.33 abcd	4.79 ab
10	0	33.3	33.5	4.43	5.29 abcd	4.87 ab
11	44.6	22.4	0	4.27	5.48 abcd	4.88 ab
12	22.4	44.6	0	3.98	4.83 abcd	4.41 bc
13	0	44.6	22.4	3.74	5.81 ab	4.77 ab
14	0	22.4	44.6	4.38	6.05 a	5.22 a
15		Control ^c		3.72	3.97 e	3.85 d
		Year mean		4.15	5.57*	
		CV (%)		12.11	9.90	10.80

^aAS = at sowing, DS = days after sowing. ^bMeans followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. LSD for years 0.75 t/ha at 5% level. Plot size was 13.94 m². ^cControl = no nitrogen. applied.

ecology, was dibbled at 30- × 30-cm spacing in mid-June and harvested in mid-December. During August to October the water depth in the experimental field ranged between 60 and 133 cm.

The results of the study indicate that application of 67 kg N/ha increased the

paddy yields highly significantly compared with the control. The time of application and split combinations did not show a consistent pattern of response. However, the effect of arrangements of time and splitting as in treatments 8 and 14 appears to be comparatively consistent and useful. ■

Iron coating on rice roots

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Oxidation and precipitation of ferrous iron in soil result in an iron coating on rice roots. The quantitative determination of the iron coating by dithionite-citrate-bicarbonate extraction revealed that cultivar, plant growth stage, and soil type influenced the quantity of iron compound on the roots. When grown on three east Texas soils (two Alfisols and a Vertisol) the cultivar Brazos had the highest iron coating accumulation (14% of the dry root weight) and highest

grain yield compared with cultivars Lebonnet, Labelle, and Bluebelle. When grown on another Vertisol, Brazos ranked second to Labelle in amount of coating and grain yield.

The high levels of iron coating associated with Brazos are believed to be related to the high amount of O₂ that its roots release in vitro.

The accumulation of iron (as FeOOH) was less than 2% of dry root weight for all cultivars within 7 days after soil flooding (plants about 35 days from emergence) and increased to an average cultivar maximum of 10% at plant maturity. Tanaka and others have reported that root-panicle ratio of rice in pots ranged from 20% to 100%. Assuming that rice plants produce 5,000 kg dry roots/ha, that iron coating is 10% of the

dry root weight, and that 1/2 of the oxygen in FeOOH is from the atmosphere, it was estimated that 6,300 liters of O₂ (31,500 liters of air)/ha would diffuse down the rice plant stem to precipitate Fe on the root.

The FeOOH was purified from extraneous materials such as quartz and layer silicate in the root coating by ultrasonication followed by high gradient magnetic separation. X-ray diffraction analysis of the final mixture (50% FeOOH) identified goethite (α-FeOOH) and lepidocrocite (γ-FeOOH) as the predominant minerals comprising the root-coating material.

Scanning electron microscope examination shows that a mature rice root has an abundance of open lumens resulting from decomposition of epidermal cells